

**EXPLORING THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN PROMOTING
NUTRITION AND HEALTH BENEFITS OF NUTRI-CEREALS PRODUCTS****A. Anisha,**Research Scholar, Alagappa Institute of Management,
Alagappa University, Karaikudi-630004, Tamilnadu, India.**Dr. K. Chandrasekar,**Professor cum Placement Officer, Alagappa Institute of Management,
Alagappa University, Karaikudi-630004, Tamilnadu, India**ABSTRACT**

Digital platforms have revolutionized the promotion of nutritious food products, particularly Nutri-cereals, by enhancing consumer awareness, accessibility, and market demand. This study explores the role of digital platforms, including social media, e-commerce, mobile applications, and digital marketing, in promoting the nutritional and health benefits of Nutri-cereal products. Findings reveal that digital platforms effectively increase awareness, with social media campaigns and online advertisements playing a significant role in influencing consumer knowledge and purchasing decisions. However, challenges such as misinformation, lack of interactive content, and difficulties in distinguishing genuine advertisements remain barriers to consumer trust. The study highlights the need for more engaging, transparent, and educational digital strategies to maximize the potential of digital platforms in encouraging Nutri-cereal consumption.

Keywords:

Digital platforms, Nutri-cereals, Nutrition awareness, Health benefits and Digital marketing strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital platforms are emerging as powerful tools in promoting and encouraging the adoption of nutritious food choices, particularly Nutri-cereals. These grains, including millets and sorghum, are rich in essential nutrients and contribute to a balanced diet (Kumar et al., 2023). Given the rising prevalence of malnutrition and lifestyle-related diseases, digital technologies can play a crucial role in enhancing consumer awareness, improving accessibility, and increasing demand for Nutri-cereal products (FAO, 2021). Nutri-cereals contribute to various health advantages, including supporting digestive health, regulating blood sugar levels, and boosting overall well-being. (Safdar et al., 2025). However, despite their nutritional advantages, these grains remain underutilized due to limited consumer awareness and restricted market accessibility. Digital platforms can help bridge this gap by disseminating information on their health benefits, culinary applications, and availability (Verma et al., 2021). The rapid expansion of digital tools has transformed the way information is shared, creating new opportunities for promoting nutrition and health awareness. In recent years, digital technologies have played a key role in educating consumers about the nutritional value of various food products, including Nutri-cereals. These grains have gained increasing attention due to their high nutritional content, climate resilience, and potential to address malnutrition and food security challenges (FAO, 2021). Rich in fiber, protein, iron, and essential micronutrients, Nutri-cereals serve as an excellent dietary choice for improving overall health and well-being (Adefegha et al., 2018). Various digital platforms, including social media, mobile applications, e-commerce websites, and digital marketing channels, have become essential in promoting the benefits of Nutri-cereals. By leveraging these tools, stakeholders including policymakers, health professionals, food manufacturers, and consumers can help close the knowledge gap surrounding the importance of incorporating these grains into daily diets. Additionally, digital platforms enable direct consumer engagement by offering personalized nutritional advice, online recipe sharing, and interactive content that enhances awareness and encourages the adoption of Nutri-cereals (Kumar et al., 2022).

1.1 Role of Digital Platforms

- *Consumer Education and Awareness:* Digital platforms serve as effective tools for educating consumers about the nutritional benefits of Nutri-cereals through infographics, videos, blogs, and expert discussions.

Government agencies, NGOs, and private-sector actors have increasingly utilized social media campaigns to highlight the role of these grains in combating malnutrition (FAO, 2021).

- *E-Commerce and Market Access*: Online marketplaces have expanded access to Nutri-cereal products by connecting producers with consumers (Rao et.al, 2021). Digital platforms allow small-scale farmers and entrepreneurs to reach a wider audience, increasing the demand and consumption of these nutritious grains.
- *Personalized Nutrition and Mobile Applications*: With the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, mobile applications provide users with personalized dietary recommendations, tracking features, and meal planning assistance based on individual health needs. These innovations have helped integrate Nutri-cereals into modern diets, addressing dietary deficiencies (Chhabra et al., 2023).
- *Policy Advocacy and Public Health Campaigns*: Digital advocacy platforms help drive policy discussions on the inclusion of Nutri-cereals in national nutrition programs, school feeding initiatives, and food security strategies (Amir et al., 2024). Policymakers and researchers leverage digital tools to disseminate research findings and mobilize support for promoting these grains as a staple food option.
- *Community Engagement and Behaviour Change*: Social media platforms and digital forums provide interactive spaces for knowledge exchange, cooking demonstrations, and testimonials on the benefits of Nutri-cereals. These community-driven initiatives encourage behaviour change and long-term adoption of healthier dietary habits (Thakur et al., 2024).

Figure:1 Digital Health Platforms

Source: Kelly et al. (2020)

1.2 Nutrition content in Nutri-cereals

In India, different varieties of millets are grown alongside other agricultural crops. They are very nutritious and have many benefits for human health. Finger millet or ragi is the most common millet consumed in Indian homes. Ragi is naturally gluten-free and high in fiber, making it beneficial for digestive health. It is also a good source of protein, iron, calcium and anti-oxidants. Foxtail millet, commonly known as Kangni, is consumed both in its whole grain form and as flour. It is very rich in protein, iron, calcium etc. Pearl millet, also known as bajra, is a gluten-free grain packed with protein, iron, calcium, and dietary fiber. Similarly, sorghum millet or jowar serves as a valuable source of protein, fiber, and magnesium. Millets contribute to weight management, lower the risk of colon cancer, help reduce high blood pressure, slow down muscle degeneration, improve sleep quality, and ease menstrual discomfort. Research by Eunyong (Lee et al., 2023) indicates that millet seed oil activates β -catenin signalling, which supports hair growth and may be effective in preventing or treating androgenetic alopecia.

Table 1: Comparison of Nutritional content in Millet

S. No	Millet	Iron (mg)	Calcium (mg)	Minerals (gms)	Fibre (gms)	Protein (gms)
1	Peral millet	11	42	2.2	2.3	11.8
2	Finger millet	3.9	344	2.7	3.6	7.3
3	Foxtail millet	2.8	31	4	6.7	12.3
4	Kodo millet	1.7	35	2.6	5.2	8.3
5	Little millet	9.3	17	1.7	7.6	7.7
6	Sorghum Millet	5.4	25	1.2	2	10.4
7	Wheat	1.8	33	0.6	1	6.8
8	Rice	3.5	30	1.5	2	11.8

Source: ICMR- National Institute of Nutrition

1.3 Health benefits of Millets

Millets are rich in various nutrients and bioactive compounds that contribute to health benefits when included regularly in the diet. Millets are hidden source for health promoting phytochemicals, and antioxidant as nutraceuticals as well as functional food (Samtiya et.al, 2023). Some of the important benefits of millets are briefly described as below:

Obesity: In recent years, obesity has become a widespread issue, linked to numerous ailments like diabetes, hypertension, and cardiac issues. Consuming a fiber-rich diet can help improve digestive health and support proper bowel function, lower the prevalence of obesity, and lower the chance of developing chronic diseases by improving the body's digestion and absorption (Gupta et.al, 2024). Millets aid in controlling body weight and preventing obesity while also promoting a feeling of fullness.

Diabetes: There is a reduced incidence of diabetes among those who consume millet. Millet phenolics partly inhibit the enzymatic breakdown of complex carbs, reducing postprandial hyperglycemia in a manner similar to alpha glucosidase (Shobana et.al, 2009). According to Hegde et al. (2005), feeding finger millet to diabetic mice reduced blood glucose levels and enhanced antioxidant activity. The high fiber content of finger millet contributed to a lower glycemic response in the diet.

Cardiovascular disease: A great way to reduce the symptoms and indicators of heart attacks Consuming millets can help reduce migraines, as they are rich in magnesium, a mineral known to support nerve function and reduce the frequency of headaches. A range of phytochemicals are present in millets, such as phytic acid, which has been demonstrated to reduce cholesterol (Coulibaly et al., 2011).

Cancer: The "antinutrients" phytate, tannins, and phenolic acids are found in high concentrations in millets. Conversely, in animal studies, these antinutritional compounds have been linked to a reduced risk of breast and colon cancers. In vitro studies suggest that the phenolic compounds found in millets may play a role in inhibiting the development and progression of cancer (Chandrasekara and Shahidi, 2011).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Gandhi et.al, (2024) Digital marketplaces enabling consumers to purchase food from a variety of different sellers have proliferated rapidly in recent years. These platforms differ from conventional retailers in that they typically neither select nor take legal ownership of the food products offered for sale on their websites. They provide an affordable and low-risk opportunity for budding food entrepreneurs who may not operate from a licensed food establishment to enter the market.

Loginov et.al, (2023) The article explores the possibility of using digital platforms to improve the efficiency of national food security management. It is established that currently many countries of the world are betting on increasing the level of self-sufficiency in food as a fundamental condition for ensuring national food security.

Chan et.al, (2023) In this study, first, we review the relevant literature and apply the triple bottom line (TBL) framework to classify prior studies into economic sustainability, social sustainability, environmental sustainability, and multidimensional sustainability. We then identify three major research gaps, including inadequate investigation on the restaurant's Consumer preferences and choices, a shallow grasp of environmental impacts, and insufficient analysis of the multi-faceted sustainability aspects in third-party food delivery services remain key challenges.

Santoso et.al, (2023) The results show that food quality and price fairness have a significant effect on e-satisfaction. In addition, our findings show that e-satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention, but it shows a nonsignificant positive effect on e-WOM intention. Overall, our findings indicate that on digital platforms, ensuring customer satisfaction with product quality and perceived price fairness alone may not be sufficient, as it does not fully guarantee loyalty or continued engagement not indicate a significant relationship with the willingness of the customers to recommend it to other app users.

Fuchs et.al, (2022) Digital platforms, particularly through the use of digital food labels, have shown potential in promoting healthier food choices. A study demonstrated that a digital food label intervention led to consumers choosing products with higher nutritional quality, indicating the potential of digital platforms to influence healthier consumer behaviour.

Mahawar et.al, (2022) The rise of online food delivery platforms has changed consumer food purchasing behaviours. However, these platforms often promote discretionary and less healthy food options, which can negatively impact dietary choices. There is a need for further research to explore the direct associations between the nutritional quality of food offered on these platforms and consumer dietary choices.

Kolmykova et.al, (2021) The research focuses on instruments of digitalization of agriculture as a way of innovative optimization of its development. The effectiveness of implementing digital innovations and information technologies in agriculture lies in enhancing production efficiency, streamlining organizational and management practices, resolving specific operational conflicts, and ensuring a balance between productivity and environmental sustainability.

Bermoy et.al, (2021) the results revealed that social media does not significantly affect customer value in online food products. That means that consumers prefer traditional marketing strategies or advertisements. It can be reasonably concluded that social media has a minimal impact on the online marketing of food products. The study suggests that companies should adopt a more proactive and interactive approach with their customers, promote their products in creative and informative ways without being redundant, and pay close attention to customer feedback.

Théodore et.al, (2021) The study explores that while digital platforms can promote healthy eating, they also pose challenges. Promoting low-nutrient products through digital marketing, particularly aimed at children and teenagers, poses a serious concern. These marketing strategies often use persuasive techniques to promote products high in critical nutrients, which can undermine public health efforts.

Schiro et.al, (2020) This paper examines how organizations focused on food safety and nutrition can leverage search engines, mobile apps, games, social media platforms, and digital analytics to develop impactful and wide-reaching digital communication strategies. We start with search engines, showing how organisations can identify popular food safety and nutrition queries, facilitating the creation of timely and in-demand content.

Rangaswamy et.al, (2020) this paper explores their salient characteristics, the role of marketing in helping DBPs succeed, and important research topics for theory and practice. A new conceptual framework based on insights from transaction cost analysis outlines the role and impact of marketing in DBPs. A key role for marketing is to increase the number and quality of interactions on a DBP while reducing transaction costs for users and production costs for the DPB.

Zarnowieckiengae et.al, (2020) Digital platforms, including websites and apps, have been effective in promoting nutrition among children by targeting parents, who are the primary gatekeepers of children's diets. These platforms can improve nutrition outcomes, self-efficacy, and knowledge among parents. Successful digital interventions often include interactive features and evidence-based information, which are crucial for engaging users and promoting dietary changes.

Jayaprakash et.al, (2019) Digital platforms have become an integral part of user-experience innovation in a short period of time. These interviews have helped in creating knowledge on the change drivers for prosumer driven 3d food printing, nature of the prosumer platform, future of food, and the potential use-cases for prosumer driven 3d food printing systems. Overall, the qualitative research data implies that leveraging 3d food printing technology and digital platforms would generate value chains that are transparent, data-driven, connected, collaborative, and sustainable. This study primary focus on the role of digital platforms in promoting nutrition and health benefits of Nutri-cereals products. To fill the gap in the literature and to better understand how digital platforms promote the nutrition and health benefits of Nutri-cereals products, The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How do digital platforms contribute to raising awareness about the nutrition and health benefits of Nutri-cereals products?

2. What is the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies in influencing consumer perceptions and purchase decisions regarding Nutri-cereals?
3. To what extent do digital platforms impact customer engagement and trust in Nutri-cereal products?

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the effectiveness of digital platforms in raising awareness about the nutritional and health benefits of Nutri-cereals.
2. To examine the impact of digital marketing strategies on the purchasing behaviour of Nutri-cereal consumers.
3. To identify the challenges and opportunities in leveraging digital platforms for Nutri-cereal promotion.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a structured to explore the role of digital platforms in promoting the nutrition and health benefits of Nutri-cereal products. A questionnaire-based survey was used as the primary data collection tool to assess consumer perceptions regarding digital platforms' influence on awareness, engagement, and purchasing behaviour. The research targeted a diverse consumer base that actively interacts with digital platforms to obtain information about Nutri-cereals. The sample was selected using a stratified sampling method, ensuring representation from individuals familiar with digital marketing strategies and health-conscious consumers interested in Nutri-cereal products. The data collected were analysed using statistical tools to evaluate the effectiveness of digital promotions, consumer trust in online content, and the overall impact of digital engagement on purchasing decisions. The study's findings provide insights into how digital marketing strategies shape consumer awareness and trust, highlighting both the opportunities and challenges in leveraging digital platforms for nutrition promotion.

5. RESULTS

Table 1: Awareness of Nutri-cereals

Factors	Mean	Rank
I have come across information about Nutri-cereals on digital platforms	3.76	3
Digital platforms have increased my awareness of the health benefits of Nutri-cereals	4.63	1
Social media campaigns have influenced my knowledge of Nutri-cereals.	4.08	2
I actively seek information about Nutri-cereals through digital sources.	3.42	4
Educational content on digital platforms helps me understand the nutritional value of Nutri-cereals	2.96	5

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The findings suggest that digital platforms effectively raise awareness about Nutri-cereals, particularly their health benefits (mean = 4.63). Social media campaigns also significantly influence knowledge (mean = 4.08), while general exposure to information remains moderate (mean = 3.76). However, active information-seeking (mean = 3.42) and educational content impact (mean = 2.96) are lower, indicating a need for more engaging and informative digital resources.

Table 2: Influence of Digital Marketing Strategies on Purchase Behaviour

Factors	Mean	Rank
Online advertisements influence my decision to buy Nutri-cereal products	4.96	1
I am more likely to buy Nutri-cereals after reading positive reviews online	3.36	2
Digital promotions impact my purchasing decisions.	2.74	5
Influencers and bloggers affect my decision to try Nutri-cereals	3.14	4

I prefer brands that use digital platforms for promotions over those that do not	3.31	3
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Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The results indicate that online advertisements have the strongest influence on consumers' decisions to purchase Nutri-cereal products, with the highest mean score (4.96). Positive online reviews also play a significant role, ranking second (3.36), suggesting that consumer feedback impacts purchasing choices. Preference for brands using digital platforms (3.31) and influencer recommendations (3.14) further highlight the role of digital engagement in shaping consumer behaviour. However, digital promotions (2.74) have the least impact, indicating that while online presence matters, direct promotions may be less persuasive than advertisements and reviews.

Table 3: Customer Engagement and Trust

Factors	Mean	Rank
I trust Nutri-cereal brands that have a strong digital presence	3.01	4
Engaging with brands through social media increases my trust in their products	2.63	5
I prefer to buy Nutri-cereals from brands that actively interact with customers online.	3.57	2
I am more likely to try a Nutri-cereal product after engaging with an informative digital campaign	3.10	3
Customer reviews on digital platforms influence my trust in Nutri-cereal brands	4.87	1

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The findings suggest that customer reviews on digital platforms (4.87) have the strongest influence on trust in Nutri-cereal brands, highlighting the importance of peer feedback. Active brand interaction online (3.57) and informative digital campaigns (3.10) also contribute to building trust, though to a lesser extent. A strong digital presence alone (3.01) is less effective in fostering trust, while social media engagement (2.63) has the least impact. Overall, trust is primarily driven by customer experiences and reviews rather than direct brand engagement strategies.

Table 4: Challenges and Opportunities in Digital Promotion

Factors	Mean	Rank
A lack of reliable information online makes it difficult to trust Nutri-cereal products	4.22	3
Digital platforms provide an effective way to learn about Nutri-cereals.	4.63	1
More investment in digital marketing would increase my likelihood of purchasing Nutri-cereals	3.59	2
I find it difficult to differentiate between genuine and misleading digital advertisements	3.18	4
There is a need for more interactive and engaging Nutri-cereal content on digital platforms.	2.16	5

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The results indicate that digital platforms are highly effective for learning about Nutri-cereals (4.63), highlighting their potential for consumer education. Increased investment in digital marketing (3.59) could enhance purchasing likelihood, while lack of reliable information (4.22) remains a significant trust barrier. Difficulty in distinguishing genuine from misleading advertisements (3.18) further challenges consumer confidence. However, the need for more interactive content (2.16) ranks lowest, suggesting that information quality is more critical than engagement tactics.

6. FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

The study examined the influence of digital technology platforms on consumer awareness, purchasing behaviour, engagement, and trust concerning Nutri-cereal products. The results indicate that digital platforms play a crucial role in enhancing awareness about Nutri-cereals (Table 1). Social media campaigns significantly impact consumer knowledge, with a mean score of 4.08, while online advertisements emerge as a primary influence on purchase decisions, ranking highest with a mean of 4.96 (Table 2). Regarding digital marketing effectiveness, positive online reviews (mean: 3.36) and brand presence on digital platforms (mean: 3.31) substantially affect purchase decisions. However, digital promotions (mean: 2.74) and influencer marketing (mean: 3.14) rank lower in their influence compared to other factors. Customer engagement and trust are also significantly shaped by digital presence, with customer reviews (mean: 4.87) being the strongest trust factor (Table 3). Moreover, brand interaction on social media (mean: 2.63) appears less impactful, indicating that companies need to focus on enhancing direct engagement strategies.

The study also identifies challenges and opportunities in digital promotion. While digital platforms provide an effective way to learn about Nutri-cereals (mean: 4.63), the lack of reliable information online (mean: 4.22) presents a trust barrier. The results suggest that increased investment in digital marketing (mean: 3.59) could improve consumer confidence and purchasing behaviour. Additionally, distinguishing between genuine and misleading advertisements remains a concern (mean: 3.18), highlighting the need for more transparent and interactive content (Table 4). The findings demonstrate that digital platforms significantly contribute to increasing awareness and trust in Nutri-cereal products. However, the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies varies, with consumer trust heavily reliant on reliable information and positive reviews. To maximize the potential of digital platforms, brands should focus on enhancing engagement, transparency, and interactive educational content to build stronger consumer relationships and drive sustainable purchase behaviours.

7. CONCLUSION

The study confirms that digital platforms play a crucial role in promoting the nutrition and health benefits of Nutri-cereals. Social media campaigns, online advertisements, and customer reviews significantly enhance consumer awareness and influence purchasing decisions. However, while digital marketing is effective, challenges such as misinformation and low engagement with digital content hinder its full potential. To enhance the effectiveness of digital strategies, stakeholders should focus on developing transparent, informative, and interactive content that fosters consumer trust. Increased investment in digital marketing and policy advocacy can further promote Nutri-cereals as a sustainable and healthy dietary choice, ultimately contributing to improved public health outcomes.

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